

Compounds of Sulphur Trioxide with Oxygen Bases. Part IV. Cryoscopic Studies of Sulphur Trioxide Complexes in Dioxane

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Cryoscopic studies of the adducts of sulphur trioxide with fatty acids have been carried out in dioxane and it has been found that $\text{SO}_3 \cdot \text{RCOOH} \cdot \text{C}_4\text{H}_8\text{O}_2$ is the most stable species in dioxane. This has been supported by molecular weight determinations of such solvated compound in dioxane. Mode of hydrolysis of sulphur trioxide-fatty acid adducts has also been investigated.

Sulphur trioxide is well known to form donor-acceptor complexes with bases having nitrogen and oxygen donor sites. In earlier publications on the sulphur trioxide-oxygenated bases adducts¹⁻⁵, conductometric studies of these solutions have been reported to show the formation of complexes and a few compounds have actually been isolated. Peski⁶ also prepared addition compounds of sulphur trioxide with carboxylic acids but did not establish their nature. As most of these adducts are insoluble in carbon tetrachloride, nitrobenzene and nitromethane, their solution chemistry could not be studied. However, it has been found that the adducts of sulphur trioxide with fatty acids are soluble in dioxane and hence the solution chemistry of these compounds has been studied in dioxane which may be helpful in understanding their structure and is being reported here.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Sulphur trioxide forms oily viscous compounds with fatty acids. These compounds are sensitive to moisture and easily get hydrolysed. They become more viscous and develop colour on standing indicating that they polymerise with time. Sulphur trioxide is known to form two white flaky solid compounds with dioxane⁷ but these fatty acid adducts are completely miscible in dioxane and nothing separates out which suggests that these adducts are true molecular compounds and sulphur trioxide is not free to react with dioxane. Sulphur trioxide forms addition compounds with three molecules of acetic and propionic acids ($\text{SO}_3 \cdot 3\text{CH}_3\text{COOH}$ and $\text{SO}_3 \cdot 3\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{COOH}$), two molecules of butyric and isobutyric acids ($\text{SO}_3 \cdot 2\text{CH}_3(\text{CH}_2)_2\text{COOH}$ and $\text{SO}_3 \cdot 2(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{CHCOOH}$) and one molecule of caproic acid ($\text{SO}_3 \cdot \text{CH}_3(\text{CH}_2)_4\text{COOH}$.) Molecular weights of these adducts have been determined in dioxane and are reported in Table I.

1. R. C. Paul, S. P. Narula, Prabha Meyer and S. K. Gondal, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1962, **21B**, 552.
2. R. C. Paul, M. S. Bains, R. Kesh, S. S. Pahil and D. Singh, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1965, **3**, 239.
3. R. C. Paul, S. P. Narula, D. S. Bhusri, D. Singh and M. S. Bains, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1965, **3**, 247.
4. R. C. Paul and S. P. Narula, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1961, **20B**, 184.
5. R. C. Paul, S. P. Narula, and S. K. Gondal, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1965, **3**, 243.
6. A. J. Van Peskli, *Pernis Rec. trav. Chim.*, 1921, **50**, 103.
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TABLE I

Molecular weights of sulphur trioxide-fatty acid adduct in dioxane and water

Compound	F.wt.	Mol. weight in dioxane		Mol. weight in water	
		Found	Ratio F/Req.	Found	Ratio
SO ₃ .3CH ₃ COOH	260.0	90.9	0.34	45.2	0.21
SO ₃ .3C ₂ H ₅ COOH	302.0	102.2	0.33	63.8	0.21
SO ₃ .2CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₂ COOH	256.0	134.2	0.52	—	—
SO ₃ .2CH ₃ CHCOOH	256.0	130.0	0.51	76.4	0.30
SO ₃ .CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₄ COOH	196.0	270.7	—	—	—

It is evident from Table I that the value of ν , the number of particles or ions produced per mole of the solute, is three in the case of acetic and propionic acid adducts and two in case of butyric and isobutyric acid adducts as their molecular weights are one third and one half of that required by their molecular formulae. The mode of dissociation of these compounds in a simple way, may be postulated as :

suggesting that when these complexes are dissolved in dioxane, at least one molecule of acetic or propionic acid remains attached with sulphur trioxide (SO₃.RCOOH) which thus appears to be a stable species. However, SO₃.RCOOH, being high acidic species, may not remain as such in a donor solvent, therefore, the dissociation of the adduct may be better represented by equation (ii) which finds support from the fact that when an attempt was made to isolate a species of the type SO₃.RCOOH by removing dioxane under vacuum, compounds of the composition SO₃.2RCOOH.C₄H₈O₂ were obtained (Table II). Cryoscopic studies of this residual compound in dioxane (Table II) show that molecular weights determined are only half of the formulae weight suggesting that only two particles are being produced per mole of the compound and the molecular dissociation may be represented as :

TABLE II

Molecular weight of sulphur trioxide-fatty acid in dioxane

Compound	Compound in dioxane	Mol. weight		Ratio F/Req.
		Found	Required	
SO ₃ .3CH ₃ COOH	SO ₃ .2CH ₃ .COOH.C ₄ H ₈ O ₂	145.0	288.0	0.50
SO ₃ .3C ₂ H ₅ COOH	SO ₃ .2C ₂ H ₅ COOH.C ₄ H ₈ O ₂	153.8	316.0	0.49
SO ₃ .2CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₂ COOH	SO ₃ .CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₂ COOH.C ₄ H ₈ O ₂	257.0	256.0	1.00
SO ₃ .2(CH ₃) ₂ CH.COOH	SO ₃ .2(CH ₃) ₂ CH.COOH.C ₄ H ₈ O ₂	262.9	256.0	1.00
SO ₃ .CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₄ COOH	SO ₃ .CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₄ COOH.C ₄ H ₈ O ₂	284.8	284.0	1.00

Acetyl and propenyl hydrogen sulphate, are definitely strong acids in water and protonate it to form hydronium ion as :

Acetic acid and propionic acid are sufficiently strong acids due to levelling effect of water and shall produce more than one particle and hence the one fifth molecular weight can be explained. The mode of hydrolysis seems to be quite reasonable as $\text{S}(\text{OH})_6$ is not stable⁸ and $\text{RCOOS}(\text{OH})_5$ may also be unstable. Another mode of hydrolysis can be postulated as :

Though it explains the one fifth value of molecular weight it cannot explain the lower value of sulphates when determined as BaSO_4 in water which is quite reasonably explained by the first mode of hydrolysis.

In the case of butyric acid, molecular weight determined in water is only one third of molecular formulae weight which suggests that the value of ν , the number of particles produced per mole of the solute, is only three. It may be conveniently explained as

Hydrolysis cannot be explained according to equation

as it produces four particles rather than three as has been experimentally found which confirms earlier view that hydrolysis of these compounds takes place through the first reaction.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of sulphur trioxide :

Sulphur trioxide was prepared from oleum to which some phosphorus pentoxide was added in all glass one unit apparatus.

Purification of acids :

Acetic acid : Two hundred g. of glacial acetic acid was refluxed with 5 ml. of acetic anhydride for about 2 hr when the water present in acetic acid completely reacted with acetic anhydride to give acetic acid. Then the liquid was fractionally distilled and the fraction distilling at 114-115° was collected for use.

8. I. V. Yanitskii, I. N. Valanchunes and O. Ya. Tuchite, *Zhur. Neorg. Khim.*, 1958, 3, 2087.

Propionic acid : Propionic acid (Narden) was refluxed over potassium permanganate in an all glass apparatus for about 1 hr. and was followed by fractional distillation. The distillate coming at 139-141° was collected.

n-Butyric, isobutyric, iso-valeric and caproic acids : These acids were kept over anhydrous sodium sulphate for about 24 hr. The clear liquid in each case was decanted off and fractionally distilled. The respective distillates of these acids were collected at temperature given against each acid

<i>n</i> -Butyric acid	162-163°
<i>Iso</i> -butyric acid	152-154°
<i>Iso</i> -valeric acid	175-176°
Caproic acid	199-201°

Purification of carbon tetrachloride : Carbon tetrachloride was refluxed over phosphorus pentoxide in an apparatus having fractionating column packed with glass helices and take off ratio arrangement. The fraction distilling at 76-77° was collected for use as a solvent in isolating the addition compounds of fatty acids with sulphur trioxide.

Purification of dioxane : Pure grade dioxane (1 litre), concentrated hydrochloric acid (10 ml.) and water (100 ml.) were refluxed for about 12 hr in an atmosphere of nitrogen and distilled. The distillate was treated with sufficient amount of potassium hydroxide pellets to remove most of water as the lower alkali layer. The upper layer of dioxane was separated and was kept over a fresh lot of potassium hydroxide pellets for a day. The liquid was decanted off and was refluxed over sodium metal followed by distillation. The fraction of the distillate coming at 99-100° was stored for use.

Molecular weight determinations : The molecular weight determination were made in an apparatus specially designed for this purpose. Cryoscopically the apparatus was protected from moisture by guard tubes and it was connected to dry nitrogen system maintained at a very small positive pressure. The stirring was done by a magnetic bar placed in the solvent to be stirred and was operated by a stirrer placed suitably under it.

Preparation of sulphur trioxide-fatty acid adducts : The adducts of sulphur trioxide-fatty acid were prepared as described in our previous communications⁹.

Preparation of sulphur trioxide-fatty acid-dioxane compounds : The compounds of dioxane with the adducts of sulphur trioxide fatty acid were prepared by adding a little excess of dioxane into sulphur-trioxide-fatty acid adduct. The excess of dioxane was removed by applying high vacuum.